

MODELING THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF FABRIC-REINFORCED RUBBER-LIKE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: The paper presents a theoretical and numerical model applicable to large strain analysis of composite materials such as flexible hoses. A three-dimensional constitutive law which uses the concept of convected coordinate frame is developed for materials presenting elastic and orthotropic behaviors in the large deformation field. The proposed model is implemented in a finite element code and numerical examples are given to demonstrate the effectiveness of the model and the numerical algorithms. Finally, in order to compare our numerical results, an experimental device is developed to exhibit the mechanical behavior of straight flexible hoses in the case of elementary tests. The model is then compared to these experimental results.

KEYWORDS: Orthotropy, Hyperelasticity, Convected coordinates, Fabric-reinforced rubber, Flexible hose, Large deformations.

1 Introduction

In service, flexible hoses are generally submitted to a low internal pressure but to full travels and angular movements in all the directions. Therefore, the behavior of such materials involves large deformations in complex modes and the modeling of this behavior goes through a better knowledge of elementary behaviors. For example, in the case of a flexible hose made out of fabric-reinforced rubber it is necessary to take into account both the non-linear quasi-reversible behavior of the rubber and the elastic orthotropic behavior of the fabric. A first step of our study consisted in the development and the implementation in a finite element code of an hyperelastic constitutive law [1] [2] [3]. To complete the model, an orthotropic constitutive law has been studied to model the large deformations and rotations encountered in reinforcement fabrics [4]. A convected orthotropic constitutive law is then introduced in a finite element code. This code has the particularity of dealing intrinsically with large strains by using a system of material

coordinates convected by the displacement of the body. In order to compare our numerical results, an experimental device is developed to exhibit the mechanical behavior of straight flexible hoses in the case of elementary tests such as tension, compression, bending or torsion.

In the first part of this paper, the materials as well as the experimental device are described. In a second part, the theoretical formulation of the model is briefly reviewed; convected material coordinates are presented, as well as the formulation of 3D kinematics. Both the hyperelastic and the orthotropic constitutive law are presented and their integration into a finite element approach by the use of the variational formulation is also described. In the last part, the model is compared to experimental results obtained on straight flexible hoses.

2 Experimental

The flexible hoses are composed of a rubberized polyester fabric embedded between two silicon elastomer layers, each of the three layers being 2 mm thick. The mechanical properties of the elastomer layers are determined from tensile tests in order to determine the material parameters of the hyperelastic constitutive law. Those of the rubberized fabric layer are obtained from tensile tests as well as from shear tests since the constitutive behavior is chosen as orthotropic.

Silicon elastomer. As the behavior of elastomers is usually considered as isotropic [5], the identification of the material parameters is performed using only tensile tests. The samples are bone-shaped specimens of 100 mm gauge length and 2 mm thick. The results obtained on two different samples are presented Fig.1. From these curves, the stress-Almansi strain curves are calculated using the relation : $2\epsilon = (l^2 - l_0^2) / l^2$ where l_0 and l are the initial and the current gauge length of the extensometer respectively. The bulk modulus k is obtained by the relation: $k = E / 3(1 - 2\nu)$, where $E = 3(\mu_r + \mu_\infty)$ and $\nu = 0.47$ are the Young modulus and the Poisson's ratio

Figure 1: *Tensile tests performed on silicon elastomer samples and on rubberized fabric samples at 0° and 90° orientation with respect to the fiber directions of the fabric. Identification of the elastomer's behavior using parameters of Table.1.*

respectively. From these results, the material parameters which are used to identify the hyperelastic constitutive law [2] [3] are given in Table 1 (in MPa).

k	Q_0	μ_r	μ_∞
250	0.94	0.055	0.01533

Table 1: *Material parameters of the silicon elastomer layers.*

Rubberized fabric. The rubberized fabric layer is made of a polyester fabric woven at 90° and cast into a silicon elastomer layer. For tensile tests, the sample have the same shape and dimensions as for elastomeric ones. As this layer is modeled using an orthotropic constitutive law, the principal fiber directions of the fabric are tested, i.e. 0° and 90° , the tensile test results being presented Fig.1. It can be observed on this figure that the behavior is strongly non-isotropic. The shear modulus G_{12} in the layer plane is determined from shear tests using the experimental device presented in [6]. The Poisson's ratio ν_{12} is taken as the common value used for elastomer materials [5]. Finally, parameters $E_3, \nu_{13}, \nu_{23}, G_{13}, G_{23}$ of the orthotropic constitutive law are considered as negligible with respect to the parameters in the layer's plane. From these results, the material parameters which are used to identify the orthotropic constitutive law [4] are given in Table 2.

E_1 (MPa)	E_2 (MPa)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (MPa)
30	15	0.47	12

Table 2: *Material parameters of the rubberized fabric layer.*

Experimental device. An experimental device has been developed for testing straight flexible hoses under elementary tests such as tension, compression, bending and torsion. For the strains generated by the internal pressure in service ($P = 0.12$ MPa) are rather weak compared to those generated by full travels and angular movements, the mechanical tests are performed without internal pressure. The device is connected to a tensile machine of maximum load capacity of 10 kN. The measurement of the force is performed by a load cell of maximum capacity of 5 kN and the measurement of the displacement is directly given by the movable crosshead. The displacement rate is 5 mm/min.

For tensile and compression tests, the flexible hoses are set on each side in two striated adapters and tight by a flexible necklace. For bending tests, the experimental device, presented Fig.2.a, allows to test two flexible hoses together. A U-shaped plateau is connected to the movable crosshead of the tensile machine. On the lateral parts of this plateau, two flexible hoses are tight using the same adapters that are used for tensile tests. In the central axis, both flexible hoses are clamped using tensile adapters which are directly connected to the fixed crosshead of the tensile machine, see Fig.2.a. Then, when moving the plateau with respect to the central axis, an clamped-clamped bending is obtained on the flexible hoses.

For torsion tests, the device is similar to the previous one, except for the central axis, see Fig.2.b. A shaft (rotation axis) is inserted between the lateral parts of the U-shaped plateau and the central axis is connected to this shaft by two ball bearings. The rotation

Figure 2: *Experimental device for testing elementary behavior of straight flexible hoses. a) bending test and b) torsion test.*

motion of the central axis is performed from the linear displacement of the tensile machine by a rod and crank system. The flexible hoses are also clamped using tensile adapters and flexible necklace.

3 Constitutive behavior

The mechanical behavior of the elastomer layers is modeled using an hyperelastic constitutive law which has already shown its ability of well-describing the behavior of rubber-like materials. Concerning the rubberized fabric, if large deformations are considered, classical orthotropic behavior can no longer be retained because of the loss of material symmetry. In order to keep a single law, even for large deformations, the concept of convected orthotropy has been introduced [4]. This general framework has also been used to define other constitutive laws such as elastohysteresis [1] and their application to shape memory alloys and elastomers [7] [8] [2]. This section presents a brief review of the model.

Kinematics. The theoretical formulation of the model is written considering large geometrical transformations including large deformations. In that context, a general 3D kinematics involving convected material frames is studied. Let us consider a continuous body Ω in motion and M a point on this body. The position of M is defined in a fixed cartesian frame (O, \vec{I}_a) , $a = 1, 2, 3$ by its coordinates $X_{(0)}^a$ at time $t = 0$ and $X_{(t)}^a$ at time $t > 0$. To follow the point M in its motion, it is marked using curvilinear coordinates θ^i , $i = 1, 2, 3$. This marking is constant throughout the deformation and the simplest one is the coordinates in the fixed frame at $t = 0$. In the simulation and for the sake of simplicity, the curvilinear coordinates are equal to the coordinates on the reference

element. A corresponding natural frame (M, \vec{g}_i) is associated with point M :

$$\vec{g}_{i(t)} = \frac{\partial O\vec{M}(t)}{\partial \theta^i} = \frac{\partial X_{(t)}^a}{\partial \theta^i} \vec{I}_a \quad (1)$$

The $\vec{g}_{i(t)}$ vectors are calculated at time t and they evolve during the deformation. The covariant components of the metric tensor $\mathbf{G} = g_{ij(t)} \vec{g}_{(t)}^i \otimes \vec{g}_{(t)}^j$ are derived from these vectors: $g_{ij(t)} = \vec{g}_{i(t)} \cdot \vec{g}_{j(t)}$, where the contravariant or dual vectors $\vec{g}_{(t)}^i$ are defined as follows: $\vec{g}_{(t)}^i \cdot \vec{g}_{j(t)} = \delta_j^i$. A complete study of the material coordinates can be found in [9]. Finally, the Almansi strain tensor ϵ , which is expressed in the final configuration, is calculated from:

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{2} \left(g_{ij(t)} - g_{ij(0)} \right) \vec{g}_{(t)}^i \otimes \vec{g}_{(t)}^j \quad (2)$$

Hyperelastic constitutive behavior. A hyperelastic body is characterized by a strain energy density, which only depends on the evolution of the body geometry during the deformation. Let \mathcal{E} be the density of elastic energy per unit volume of strained body. The Cauchy stress tensor σ is then derived from the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial \left(\sqrt{g} \mathcal{E} \right)}{\partial t} = \sqrt{g} \sigma : \mathbf{D} \quad (3)$$

with \mathbf{D} the strain rate tensor and $g = \det|g_{ij}|$. In the case of an isotropic behavior, which is a usual assumption for rubber, the strain energy function depends only on three invariants of the strain tensor. In our case the volume variation v and the elements of a polar representation of the deviatoric strain tensor, i.e. $\overline{\Pi}_{\bar{\epsilon}}$ and $\varphi_{\bar{\epsilon}}$, are chosen. A complete description of this law as well as the definition of the parameters of the law can be found in [2] [3].

Orthotropic constitutive behavior. In the case of fabric materials, finite deformations can appear by twisting in the fibre plane without any large deformations in the direction of the fibres. The deformed material is no longer orthotropic, unless the initial behavior is the same in the main direction of the fibres. In accordance with the classical elasticity theory, these remarks lead to an anisotropic behavior defined with 21 coefficients. Anyway, it appears that the behavior along the directions corresponding to the initial main directions convected on the deformed body does not change much. This is the main idea used here to define the evolution of the initial orthotropy. The model obtained allows to keep only the 9 initial parameters from the general orthotropic behavior [4].

Let us consider a material frame of unit vectors $\vec{O}_i (i = 1, 2, 3)$ whose directions coincide with the initial direction of the fabric fibers and represents the orthotropic main directions of the body with regard to the fixed reference frame \vec{I}_a . The relation between the initial orthotropic frame and the natural frame $\vec{g}_{i(t)}$ can be defined by a rotation of angle α in the tangent plane to the medium surface of the element. The orthotropic constitutive behavior is still represented by a non constant 4th-order tensor \mathbf{E} such as:

$$\sigma = \mathbf{E} : \epsilon \quad (4)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor. In the initial condition, the coordinates of \mathbf{E} in the \vec{O}_i frame can be represented by the classical matrix of orthotropic elasticity, obtained by inverting the stiffness matrix \mathbf{S} for which terms are generally more simple. In accordance with our previous assumption, the coordinates of \mathbf{E} are assumed constant during deformation and the tensor \mathbf{E} is written in the initial orthotropic frame \vec{O}_i :

$$\mathbf{E} = E^i_{jk} \vec{O}_i \otimes \vec{O}^j \otimes \vec{O}^k \otimes \vec{O}_l \quad (5)$$

where $i, j, k, l = 1, 2, 3$. From this relation, the tensor $\hat{\mathbf{E}}$ in the deformed natural frame $\vec{g}'_{i(t)} = \vec{g}_{i(t)} / \|\vec{g}_{i(t)}\|$ is then expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{E}} &= E^i_{jk} \Gamma^i_{\alpha} \Lambda^j_{\beta} \Lambda^k_{\gamma} \Gamma^l_{\delta} g^{\beta\beta'} g^{\gamma\gamma'} \vec{g}'_{\alpha} \otimes \vec{g}'_{\beta'} \otimes \vec{g}'_{\gamma'} \otimes \vec{g}'_{\delta} \\ &= E^{\alpha\beta'\gamma'\delta} \vec{g}'_{\alpha} \otimes \vec{g}'_{\beta'} \otimes \vec{g}'_{\gamma'} \otimes \vec{g}'_{\delta} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ and $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ are the transport matrix from the orthotropic frame to the natural frame in covariant and contravariant components, and $\alpha, \beta, \beta', \gamma, \gamma', \delta = 1, 2, 3$.

Variational formulation. The weak formulation of the boundary-value problem, defined both by the boundary conditions and the equilibrium equations derived from the principle of virtual power is written in the final configuration. This leads in a standard way to a system of algebraic non-linear equations. The method which has been retained to solve this system is the Newton-Raphson method. In that respect, it is necessary to determine the stiffness of the system, i.e. the tangent linear form with respect to the degrees of freedom. The variations of different geometrical terms with respect to the degrees of freedom can be obtained in [2] for the hyperelastic constitutive law and in [4] for the orthotropic constitutive law.

4 Results

This part is devoted to the validation of the model presented in the previous part. The validation of the orthotropic behavior has already been performed in the small deformation field: firstly, the different elementary behaviors of orthotropic laminates have been compared to the theoretical results obtained in [10]. Secondly, the bending behavior of an orthotropic laminate under a sinusoidal loading of Pagano type has been compared to the Pagano's solution [11]. Both first points are in good agreement with theoretical results [4]. In this paper, the complete model is compared to several experimental cases of straight flexible hoses submitted to elementary tests. It can be noted that for all simulations, the influence of the mesh has been previously studied and that the results presented are obtained with a sufficiently fine mesh to ensure stable solutions.

The flexible hoses are composed of three layers of equal thickness 2 mm, i.e. one layer of rubberized fabric embedded in two layers of silicon elastomer. The initial orientation of the fabric is 45° with respect to the lengthwise direction. The mesh used for the simulation of flexible hoses is presented Fig.3.

The dimensions are 170 mm length, with 100 mm of gauge length and 35 mm on each lateral side for the clamped part of the flexible necklace, an inner diameter of 58 mm and a total thickness of 6 mm. Three layers of quadratic hexaedron elements represent the different layers of the flexible hose. The mesh is composed of 10 elements in the length, 3 in the thickness and 16 on the circumference. The \vec{z} axis is taken lengthwise to the hose while \vec{x} and \vec{y} are located in a section, the origin of the frame is taken on the left side of the mesh. Boundary conditions obviously depend on the type of test but for all cases, the first row of elements on one side is completely fixed, i.e. $u = v = w = 0$ for it represents the first clamped part of the hose. For tension or compression tests, the first row on the other side represents the other clamped part at the flexible necklace, which means that $u = v = 0$. For tension tests $w > 0$ and for compression tests $w < 0$. For bending tests, the first row on the other side is such that $u = w = 0$ and $v > 0$, i.e. a displacement to a cross direction. Finally, for torsion tests, two lateral parts have been added to the previous mesh in order to create a torque around the \vec{z} axis by applying a pressure on these lateral parts.

Figure 3: *Initial mesh used for the numerical simulation of the straight flexible hose behavior.*

The results presented Fig.4 feature the curves obtained in the different cases of tests. For each test, three samples have been tested to ensure the reproductibility of the results. It can be observed that there is a good agreement between experimental curves and simulated results even for finite deformations. In all other cases than tension, the results are performed for strains such as there is no buckling effects. For compression tests, simulated results obtained using parameters of Table.1 show a large discrepancy between experimental and numerical results (see Fig.4.b.Numerical Simulation 1). This is due to the fact that this test is performed using the same material parameters in tension and in compression while the behavior is non-symmetric for these tests. In order to take account of a non-symmetric behavior in tension and compression, a dependence on $\varphi_{\bar{\varepsilon}}$ is added through the material parameter $Q_0(\varphi_{\bar{\varepsilon}})$ which replaces the parameter Q_0 . The following relation is used:

$$Q_0 = \frac{Q'_0}{(1 + \gamma \cos 3\varphi_{\bar{\varepsilon}})^n} \quad (7)$$

where Q'_0, γ, n are parameters characteristic of the material. It gives a different threshold in tension ($\varphi_{\bar{\varepsilon}} = 0$) and in compression ($\varphi_{\bar{\varepsilon}} = \pi/3$), thus leading to a non-symmetric behavior. The results obtained using these parameters are presented Fig.4.b.Numerical Simulation 2. The agreement between experimental and numerical results is then satisfying for a large range of deformation. For torsion tests, the results are initially obtained in

Figure 4: Experimental and numerical results obtained on straight flexible hoses under elementary tests a) tension, b) compression, c) bending and d) torsion.

terms of rod's displacement vs load. In order to transform these curves in rotation angle vs torque, the following relation is used:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{l\lambda^2} \left(-r + \sqrt{r^2 - \frac{l\lambda^2}{2}(l\lambda^2 + 4r + l\lambda^2\Delta l)} \right) \quad (8)$$

where r is the crank's length, l is the rod's length, $\lambda = r/l$ and α is the rotation angle. These numerical results are in good agreement with experimental ones.

5 Conclusions

This paper deals with a complete study of mechanical behavior of straight flexible hoses submitted to elementary tests such as tension, compression, bending and torsion. An experimental device has been developed in order to obtain experimental results in the finite deformation field. A theoretical model has been proposed and implemented in a finite element code to simulate the experimental results. This model uses convected material frames and the constitutive behavior is described by both an hyperelastic law for elastomer layers of the hose and an orthotropic law for the rubberized fabric layer.

This model has been validated from several standard cases from which analytical solutions are established. It is shown that the orthotropic constitutive law is able to take into account the elementary coupling effects. Finally, the model is compared to experimental results obtained on straight flexible hoses and the results are in good agreement even for large deformations.

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